

Evolution of Tourism Policy in India: An overview

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Abstract *Tourism is a maximum acceptable human pastime that is able to converting the socio-cultural, financial and environmental face of the World. Tourism is one in all the most important and quickest developing industries with inside the world; it has the capacity to persuade the residing sample of communities. It is one of the maximum critical channels of cultural trade which breaks down the obstacles among humans of various elements of the world. It is the gathering of activities, offerings and industries that supply a tour enjoy such as transportation, accommodation, consuming and drinking, institutions of retail shops, entertainment, commercial enterprise and different hospitality offerings supplied for people or businesses traveling far from home.*

India is a various Country, with over 1.3 billion humans following diverse culture, tradition, languages, festivals, faith etc. Equally various are the class of tourism pastime that India gives to her humans in addition to the humans throughout the world. Such range owe in large part to the geographic, climatic and conventional multiplicity visible in India's twenty-9 states and 7 union territories. In India tourism zone changed into taken into consideration as an critical zone handiest after the Independence and authorities has brought diverse schemes and plans for its improvement. The coverage intervention in tourism improvement is pretty apparent.

Key Words: Tourism, Economic Development, Employment, Income, Policies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Development of tourism enterprise calls for tourism making plans. Tourism Planning results in tourism improvement. Tourism Planning is the manner for tourism improvement. Planning refers to techniques and approach utilized in making selections approximately the future. Tourism Planning allows in trouble fixing and arriving at selections which assist planner in accomplishing preferred objectives. Planning for tourism may be very crucial. Several Countries of the world, mainly the growing nations have these days found out the significance of tourism and blessings which it brings out. The use of macroeconomic making plans strategies for tourism area are exceedingly new. The use of macroeconomic making plans techniques for countrywide financial improvement that have been in large part applied for the reason that quit of global wide battle second, did now no longer constantly cowl tourism improvement as a selected field. The growing importance

of tourism as a supply of income, employment generation, nearby improvement, and foremost component in stability of charge for many nations has been attracting the eye of many authorities in addition to others with an hobby.

1.1 Tourism Policy in India

Tourism emerged as the biggest international enterprise of the 20th century and is projected to develop even quicker with inside the 21st century. India has big opportunities of increase with inside the tourism region with substantial tradition and spiritual heritage, numerous herbal attractions, however a relatively small function with inside the international tourism scene. Tourism coverage strengthens the tourism region and envisages new tasks toward making tourism the catalyst in employment generation, environmental regeneration, improvement of faraway regions and improvement of girls and different deprived corporations with inside the country. It could result in large for ex profits and create situations for extra overseas direct investment.

India's tourism plans began after independence. A conscious and prepared effort to sell tourism in India was made in 1945 when the Commission was established by a government led by Sir John Sargent, then Educational Advisor to the Government of India. (Krishna.A.G.1993). Since then, India's tourism industry has been systematically improved. The tourism planning method was developed in the second and third 512-month plans. The sixth 512-month plan emphasizes tourism as a tool for economic improvement, integration and continued social harmony. Since the 1980s, interest in tourism has increased as job creators, sources of income, foreign exchange income, and the entertainment industry. Authorities have taken many major steps to sell the tourism industry.

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2. TOURISM POLICY 1982

The First Tourism policy was announced by the Government of India on November 1982. The mission of First Tourism Policy was to promote sustainable tourism as means of economic growth, social integration and to

promote the image of India abroad as a country with a glorious past, a vibrant present and a bright future. Policies to achieve this will be evolved around six broad areas such as Welcome (Swagat), Information (Suchana), Facilitation (Suvidha), Safety (Suraksha), Cooperation (Sahyog) and Infrastructure Development (Samrachana). This policy also gives importance to conservation of heritage, natural environment, development and promotion of tourist products. The objectives of tourism development are to foster understanding between people, to create employment opportunities and bring about socioeconomic benefits to the community, particularly in the interior and remote areas. We also strive for balance, sustainable development, and the preservation, strengthening and promotion of Indian cultural heritage. One of the main objectives is the conservation and protection of natural resources and the environment to achieve sustainable development. Given the low cost of job creation in the tourism sector and the low utilization of India's tourism potential, the new tourism policy is by avoiding possible adverse effects such as cultural pollution and environmental minimization. Deterioration, which aims to increase the arrival of foreign tourists and promote domestic tourism in a sustainable way. The new tourism policy also aims to make foreign tourists staying in India a memorable and enjoyable experience with predictable cost and reliable service, so repeated visits to India as friends are encouraged. It has been. It follows the traditional Indian philosophy of giving guests the highest honor (Athithi devo bhava).

2.1 Highlights of tourism policy 1982:

1. The coverage emphasis that improvement of tourism is hooked up to central, country and district level, public quarter and personal quarter.

2. The coverage encourages people to take part in tourism improvement and additionally create hobby in nearby youth.

3. The coverage encourages public personal partnership for tourism growth.

4. Realizing that tourism is a multi -sectoral interest the coverage guarantees inter-governmental linkages and co-ordination.

5. The coverage states that tourism improvement relies upon on personal quarter. Private quarter has to construct and manipulate traveler facility, hold it, preserve it, contain nearby community, construct safety and so on to broaden tourism.

6. The function of voluntary organizations and volunteers in tourism improvement is diagnosed with the aid of using the coverage.

7. The coverage implies to facilitate large budget to tourism infrastructure.

8. The coverage acknowledges that excessive first-rate requirements in services, inns and tourism associated industries are required of overseas investment.

9. The coverage shows giving precedence to technological development specially to facts technology.

10. The coverage shows for protection and safety of tourism quarter.

11. Through authorities organizations the coverage gives centers like acquiring visas, immigration checks, prices and so on.

12. The coverage creates tourism financial zones, circuits and tourism areas.

13. The coverage introduces potential plans, conservation of herbal surroundings and cultural heritages, value effectiveness and so on. In quick this coverage has succeeded in offering a sturdy coverage basis for Tourism Development within side the us of a specializing in co-ordination of all tourism associated activities, Public Private Partnership, Voluntary Organizations, Infrastructure Development, Foreign Direct Investment, Information Technology, Creation of Tourism Economic Zones and Sustainable Tourism improvement.

3. 7TH FIVE-YEAR PLAN ON TOURISM PLANNING IN INDIA ARE:

1. Actively promote domestic tourism. 2. He focused on creating more resorts. 3. Organize conferences, trekking conferences and winter sports to have different options for foreign tourists. These policies of the seventh five-year plan in India have promoted tourism planning in India.

3.1 Tourism Policy in the 8-Year Plan:

To encourage tourism planning in India, the Eighth Five-Year Plan (1992-1997) emphasized that the private sector should increase its involvement in the tourism sector. The Coalition Government has provided various means for the development of the tourism industry including the publication of the National Tourism Action Plan in 1992. The National Tourism Action Plan was published in May, 1992. The objectives of this action plan for tourism planning in India are: first. Socio-economic development of tourist areas. 2. Increase job opportunities in tourism. 3. Develop domestic tourism for budget or economic category. 4. Conservation of the environment and national heritage. 5. Encourage international tourism. 6. Increase India's share of world tourism. 7. Diversify tourism products.

3.2 National Tourism policy 2002:

The publication of the National Tourism Policy by the Government of India in 2002 was an important milestone in tourism planning in India. This Tourism Policy 2002 is based on a multi-faceted approach, including faster implementation or faster development of tourism projects of integrated tourism circuits, capacity building in the hospitality sector and new marketing strategies. The main objective of the 2002 National Tourism Policy was to place tourism as a key driver of economic growth. The government strives to achieve this goal by promoting domestic and international tourism, developing tourism infrastructure, developing new destinations, promoting agro-rural tourism, tourist routes, etc. new calendar and public-private partnership. I. Development of tourism products or destinations: The 2002 National Policy emphasizes the promotion of existing tourism products and destinations. For tourism product development and destination development, the central government has supported the state government, and major projects have been funded.

ii. Integrated development of tourist routes: The central government has provided funding to the state government to develop tourist routes of international standards.

iii. Support large revenue-generating projects: This policy has emphasized public-private partnerships to implement large revenue-generating projects such as convention centers, golf courses, yachts and cruise ships, used by tourists and generates substantial revenue for the state.

iv. Supporting public-private partnerships in infrastructure: This policy recognized that private financial resources as well as technology and management talent were needed for the development of tourism infrastructure. . So the government provides funding to organize a study tour in India, expo abroad, advertising, etc.

3.3 Tourism Tenth Year Plan Initiative (2002-2007)

The 10th Five-Year Plan under the 2002 national tourism policy framework advocates for skills enhancement by promoting training programs in the hospitality and food industries. The 10th Five-Year Plan has promoted Himalayan adventure tourism, coastal beach tourism. Wellness tourism includes traditional health practices such as Ayurveda, shopping malls for traditional handicrafts, and pilgrimage sites.

3.4 11th Five-Year Plan Tourism Initiative (2007-12)

The 11th Five-Year Plan has allocated more capital for tourism development. With the expansion of the National Tourism Policy in 2002, the 11th Five-Year Plan attempted to foster partnerships between central government, the public and the private sector. Some selected areas for funding include Srirangam, Vellore Fort (heritage destination), Pudacherry and Chennai Beach (navigation), Wayanad in Kerala, Udhagamandalam, Madumalai, Anaimalai tours in Tamil Nadu (ecotourism), Jammu and Kashmir and Northeastern states have paid special attention and are also trying to diversify tourism marketing sources. government initiatives: The Ministry of Tourism undertakes various initiatives to promote tourism in the country.

This includes: Infrastructure development: Adequate infrastructure is essential for the development of tourism. The Ministry of Tourism has endeavored to develop quality tourism infrastructure in tourist spots and circuits.

The ministry has launched a program to develop significant domestic and international destinations and tours through megaprojects. Infrastructure development schemes for tourism in India are:

1. Tourism product or infrastructure and destination development. 2. Integrated development of tourist circuits. 3. Assistance for large revenue generating project. 4. Capacity building for rural tourism. 5. Public private partnership in infrastructure development. 6. Tourism market development for domestic tourism. Marketing and promotion initiatives: Government of India initiated number of measures to promote tourism marketing and the important marketing and promotion initiatives are: Incredible India Campaign: Incredible India Campaign was introduced by the Government of India in 2002 to promote India as an ultimate tourist destination on the world tourism map. Incredible India campaign was conducted globally to attract tourists to the country. It projected India as an attractive tourist destination by showcasing Indian culture, history, spirituality and yoga.

3.5 Atithi Devo Bhavah:

Atithi Devo Bhavah is a programme conducted by the Government of India to complement the Incredible India Campaign. Main aim is to create awareness about the effect of tourism and sensitize people about our country's rich heritage, culture, cleanliness and warm hospitality. Atithi Devo Bhavah is a seven point's programme of hospitality and training. Components of Atithi Devo Bhavah are ,Samvedan sheelth or Sensitization. , Prashikshan or Training induction. Chapter Motivation Preranou. Certified Pramani karanou. Reply or Respond. Samanya Bodh Conscience. Ownership or Ownership.

3.6 Visit India 2009:

The main vision of the Visit India 2009 campaign is to promote the flow of visitors and tourism after the 2008 Mumbai terror attacks as well as the global economic crises. The program is jointly announced by the Ministry of Tourism and the World Travel and Tourism Council. This program is in effect from April to December 2009 and is supported by the hotel industry, tour operators and travel agencies and airlines.

3.7 Various tourism products:

The Indian government has introduced a number of tourism products such as rural tourism, cruise tourism, adventure tourism, medical tourism, open sky policy, etc.

3.8 Foreign Direct Investment:

The Indian government has allowed 100% foreign direct investment in the hotel and tourism industry. Hotel means restaurants, resorts and other tourist complexes providing accommodation and food services.

For tourists. The tourism industry includes tour operators, tour operators, travel agencies for tourists and cultural experiences, adventure and wildlife facilities, and land vehicles. , air and sea, fun, entertainment, sports, health and conventions, etc. In the 11th Five-Year Plan (2007-2012), there was a marked change in the approach to tourism development compared to previous plans. The tourism industry's vision for the 11th FYP is to "achieve an exceptional quality of life through the development and promotion of tourism, to provide a unique opportunity to invigorate, rejuvenate the spirit, uplift the culture and uplift the spirit". This tourism development vision has been proposed to be achieved through the following strategic objectives. a) Positioning and maintaining tourism development as a national priority. b) Improve and maintain India's competitiveness as a tourist destination. c) Improve and expand product development. d) Create world-class infrastructure. e) Develop effective marketing plans and programs and f) Human resource development and capacity building of service providers. Tourism development programs in the 11th 5-year plan Several plans have been put in place during the eleventh phase of the five-year plan to achieve the goals. To achieve the goals outlined in the 11th FYP, the Ministry of Tourism implemented the following programs during 2007-2012. Development of Destination and Tour Product Infrastructure (PIDDC). Overseas promotion and advertising, including market development support. Promote and publicize nationwide. Support big revenue generating projects. Preferential hosting infrastructure. Create land fund Support for Central Agencies Market research includes a twenty-year perspective plan. Computer and information technology According to the 11th Plan document of the Planning Commission,

"Tourism is the largest service industry in the country. Its importance lies in the fact that it is a tool for economic development and job creation, especially in remote areas". In the 11th Five-Year Plan, efforts were made to exploit the full potential of the tourism industry by improving the tourism infrastructure, disseminating it further through the Incredible India campaigns. overseas, promoting niche products such as MICE, health and wellness centers, adventure tourism, and so on.

4. TOURISM POLICY IN THE 12TH 5-YEAR PLAN

The 12th Five-Year Plan (2012-2017) introduced a new dimension of tourism's contribution. The plan highlights the need for a 'pro-poor tourism' approach to increase the net benefits from tourism to the poor and to ensure that tourism growth contributes to poverty alleviation. The approach paper also emphasizes the need to develop a comprehensive set of strategies for a range of actions, from macro to micro levels, including product and infrastructure development, marketing, shaping corporate image, branding and promotion, planning, policy and investment.

The 12th Five-Year Plan prepared by the Planning Commission highlights the following issues related to the tourism sector. I. Along with construction, tourism is one of the largest service industries in India. It can provide employment to a wide range of job seekers, from the unskilled to the skilled, even in remote parts of the country.

II. Tourism and hospitality are diverse industries that are a collection of activities, including transportation and accommodation, food and beverage establishments, retail stores, entertainment businesses, and business services. Hotels provided for individuals or groups traveling away from home for leisure, business or other purposes. A wide range of tourism-related economic activities allows for a broad spectrum of tourism growth, including informal sector participation. III. The interaction of tourists, commercial suppliers, host governments and host communities in attracting and welcoming tourists and other visitors, generating both demand and resources. supply of a wide range of tourism-related goods and services. Therefore, tourism has good potential to promote overall economic growth. IV. In 1992, the "Earth Summit" in Rio established three principles of environmental, economic and social sustainability. Since then, the principles of sustainable tourism have been adopted by the tourism industry worldwide. In India, the tourism sector is based on exploiting its unique richness of biodiversity, forests, rivers and its cultural and heritage riches. The challenges of the field include successfully preserving them in their original form and making them accessible to domestic and international visitors. Tourism in India has the potential to spark an economic interest in the local community in protecting its natural and cultural resources, leading to more sustainable growth.

4.1 Various Targets for Tourism Sector in 12th Five Year Plan:

As the tourism industry is one of the key components of the service sector in India, the country's growth targets should be aligned with the service sector growth target in the 12th Five-Year Plan. Indian economy is expected to grow at a rate of 9%. To achieve this, the service industry as well as the tourism industry must grow at a rate of 12% per year. In order to improve the growth rate of the tourism industry, the following targets have been set for Outbound Visitors (FTA) and Domestic Tourism. Increasing India's share of international tourist arrivals by at least 1% by the end of the 12th Plan, which calls for an annual growth rate of 12.38% between 2011-2016. Provide adequate facilities for domestic tourism to maintain growth of 12.16% in the 12th Plan (2011-2016). Using data on the share of the tourism industry in total national employment contained in the Tourism Satellite Account (TSA) for 2002-03. It is estimated that total employment (direct and indirect) in the tourism industry in 2016 will be 77.5 million compared to 53 million in 2010. 24.5 million jobs (direct and indirect) will be created between 2010 and 2016. Based on research commissioned by the Ministry of Tourism, employment estimates for 2012-13 is 43.84 lakh and could reach 63.79 lakh in 2016-17.

5. CONCLUSION

Tourism development and tourism policy are closely related. The development of tourism largely depends on tourism policy. Tourism is a very important segment of the economy. The economic development of any country whether developing, developed or underdeveloped is greatly influenced by the tourism sector. Therefore, each country in the world has developed some tourism policies to develop the tourism industry. The Indian government has also taken a number of initiatives to attract domestic and foreign tourists. The expansion of tourism infrastructure, development of tourist attractions, development of new tourism products Public-private partnership is some of the measures. During the post-independence period from the Indian government, the Ministry of Tourism introduced several policies to develop the tourism industry in India. Tourism has been recognized as an industry by the planning commission of India and has been included in the concurrent list of the Indian constitution to provide constitutional recognition for the tourism sector and help channel develop tourism in a systematic way to facilitate the central government to pass legislation.

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